

Personal ID

Government Agency :
 Sex : Male Female
 Age :
 Echelon : II III IV Functional
 Education : Bachelor/Master/Doctorate/other
 Please specify

Have you ever worked with : Yes, please continue
 government information? No, stop here. Thank you.

Score

1	Strongly disagree	2	Disagree	3	Neither agree nor disagree	4	Agree	5	Strongly agree
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1. The Independent Variables.

Questions on Perceived Benefits

To what extend do you agree with the statement Open Government Data will make government?

No.	Statements	Score				
		1	2	3	4	5
1.	Increased Transparency	1	2	3	4	5
2.	Improved public relations and attitudes toward government	1	2	3	4	5
3.	Increased reputation of a public sector body	1	2	3	4	5
4.	Increased government incentives	1	2	3	4	5
5.	Improved government services	1	2	3	4	5
6.	Better understanding and management of data within public sector bodies	1	2	3	4	5
7.	Stimulating economic growth	1	2	3	4	5
8.	Minimizing errors when working with government data	1	2	3	4	5
9.	Cost reduction and efficiency	1	2	3	4	5

Questions on Risk related to OGD

To what extend do you agree with the statement that OGD will risk of?

No.	Statements	Score				
		1	2	3	4	5
1.	Publication of data against the law	1	2	3	4	5
2.	More supervision from public	1	2	3	4	5
3.	Privacy infringement	1	2	3	4	5
4.	Publication of improper data or information	1	2	3	4	5
5.	Misinterpretation of the data	1	2	3	4	5
6.	Overlapping of data	1	2	3	4	5
7.	Increased number of requests for data	1	2	3	4	5

8.	Risk Losing of valuable data (sharing to other organization will risk of losing data)	1	2	3	4	5
9.	Political involvement	1	2	3	4	5
10.	High cost	1	2	3	4	5

Questions on Organizational Readiness

To what extent do you agree that factors below influence the readiness of organization to open government data?

No.	Statements	Score				
1.	IT Infrastructure	1	2	3	4	5
2.	Internal Regulation	1	2	3	4	5
3.	Internal Leadership (President, Minister, Echelon I)	1	2	3	4	5
4.	Regular trainings	1	2	3	4	5
5.	Budget allocation	1	2	3	4	5
6.	Reward and punishment	1	2	3	4	5
7.	Supporting unit to Data Custodian unit	1	2	3	4	5

Questions on External Influences

To what extent do you agree with the factors below encourage the adoption of OGD?

No.	Statements	Score				
1.	External Leadership (President)	1	2	3	4	5
2.	Indonesia membership in international organization	1	2	3	4	5
3.	Public demand in OGD	1	2	3	4	5
4.	SDI Act	1	2	3	4	5

2. The Dependent Variable

Questions on One Data Indonesia for Sustainable Development

To what extent do you agree with the factors below encourage the adoption of OGD?

No.	Statements	Score				
1.	Your ministry or agency or regional government regularly updates the content of OGD	1	2	3	4	5
2.	Your ministry or agency or regional government regularly reviews the variety of OGD that can be enhanced	1	2	3	4	5
3.	Your ministry or agency or regional government regularly promotes the OGD data set	1	2	3	4	5